

Decision support system in health care building design based on case-based reasoning and reinforcement learning

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ABSTRACT

The health care building designing is a very difficult process in which there are a great quantity of parameters and variables that it is necessary to consider. The health care building should reach the population needs. Additionally, the design of this type of building and the related facilities involves a great quantity of regulations which they are adapted to the different countries. Thus, the health care facilities should be designed according to numerous and complex regulations. The checking of this regulation is very difficult and usually involves big teams of specialized engineers and architects. The proposed Case-Based Reasoning (CBR) and Reinforcement Learning can analyse the data about building design (provided in an Extended Mark-up Language or XML file, and other compatible formats), checking, and validating the regulations. This approach allows to reduce the specialized and high qualified personnel, providing a report with the checking regulations, and the traceability of warning and faults in the application of regulations.

1. Introduction

The health care building and related facilities designing involve a lot of quantity of parameters, constraints, and regulations. The designing and checking of all these constraints require the participation of engineers, architects, and other high qualified personnel. Additionally, the project must be validated by a public and official entity to validate the proposed design according to the current regulations. This process takes a high economic, time, and personal cost. As it is mentioned in (Silva et al., 2020), the Artificial Intelligence has been an enabler and facilitator of industrial informatics with varying degrees of interest and success over time.

In this paper, a Decision Support System (DSS) based on Case-Based Reasoning (CBR) and Reinforcement Learning (RL) is proposed to provide a validation and checking system of the building and its facilities, according to the current regulations and using the specification of project in a standard file based on Extended Mark-up Language (XML). The contribution of this paper meets with the advantages which the proposed system provides:

- The reduction of validation and checking of the project.

- The reduction of time invested on the checking and validation project.
- The extraction of knowledge from building design and validation with the constraints established by current regulations.
- The reports provided by the system could be used for educational purposes.

The proposed solution is described below. Firstly, the literature review is included. Secondly, the architecture of proposed solution is described. Thirdly, the description of information resources and the standard file specifications are specified. Fourthly, the description of CBR and the generated knowledge are shown. Finally, the experimental results and conclusions are shown.

2. Literature review

In 1992, Pearce et al. (1992) tried to find out whether a large case library could support human decision making in a complex task as design, proposing Archie system. In the last decade, researchers have explored applying machine learning techniques to generate and evaluate design models before physically employing them in the construction (Hong et al., 2020) reviewed the research and applications of

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machine learning across all major stages of the building life cycle: design, construction, operation and maintenance, control, and retrofit. Findings from this study show that building design has attracted the largest research interest (44%) (Marcher et al., 2020) identifies, by means of a systematic literature review, the methods for decision making in building construction and the lifecycle phases for which decision support systems are proposed. Most of the applications of decision support systems are proposed for the construction phase and the design phase (Multiple criteria decision analysis or MCDA, machine learning, genetic algorithms).

The analysis of building design is a complex field (Roth et al., 2020): It consists of feature (Structure, facade), shape (Proportion, symmetry), function (sacred building, secular building) and symbolism (representation, lightness) analysis. In first place (Silvestre et al., 2016), determined whether an Artificial Intelligence system using deep convolutional neural network will be able to imagine architecture, by means of algorithms can be affiliated to the research field of generative architecture based on 3D models. Thus, establishing shape grammar with this automated system opens prospects for generative architecture with image-base rendering algorithms. Additionally, other approaches worked with topology of building: (Oxman & Oxman, 1993) presented an approach to a memory structure of design ideas in a library of design precedents; (Oh et al., 2019) proposes an artificial intelligent (AI)-based deep generative design framework that is capable of generating numerous design options, which are not only aesthetic but also optimized for engineering performance; (Steadman & Mitchell, 2010) provided a classification of built forms, to understand their interrelationships in a systematic way, and to see how building types have followed characteristic morphological trajectories through this space of forms, in a geometrical point of view; (Lin, 2013) developed a tool entitled Visual Architectural Topology for encoding topological information within a case library by applying an ontology-based topological validation mechanism, extending the knowledge representation ability of a design case library (semantic and geometric design information); (de Miguel et al., 2019) presented a methodology for generation, manipulation and form finding of structural typologies using variational autoencoders, a machine learning model based on neural networks.

Other approaches are based on the conceptual or functional design of the buildings (Cavieres et al., 2011) described the first phase of development of a CBR system to support early conceptual design of buildings, focusing on energy performance of commercial buildings. However (Ayzenshtadt et al., 2016), proposed a Rule-Based and Case-Based Retrieval Coordination to support the early conceptualization phase in architecture, developed in the framework of Metis project (Zhang, 2018) describes CityMatrix, a machine learning approach based on convolutional neural networks to achieve real-time prediction of multiple urban simulations and thousands of city configurations, focused on traffic and solar performance (Eisenstadt et al., 2020) presented a system for case-based retrieval of architectural designs in the form of graph-based room configuration by means of applying a case preselection process using a convolutional neural network and the subsequent graph and subgraph matching on the preselected cases, developed in context of a bigger framework (Eisenstadt et al., 2019) presented an approach for computer-aided generation of different variations of floor plans during the early phases of conceptual design in architecture, based on a CBR and methodology FLEA (Find, Learn, Explain, Adapt) (Richter & Donath, 2006) focused on the CBR in architectural design and education, making a critical review.

Also, many studies have proposed Automatic Rule Checking (ARC) method in design (Amor & Dimyadi, 2021) reviews evolving approaches for automated compliance checking, addressing challenges in sharing digital architectural and engineering design information, formalizing normative provisions as computable rules, and methods of processing them for compliance (Eastman et al., 2009) examines rule checking systems that assess building designs after they are generated; (Zhang

et al., 2013) applies automated safety rule checking to Building Information Models (BIM). As a result, the developed automated safety checking platform informs construction engineers and managers by reporting, why, where, when, and what safety measures are needed; (Solihin & Eastman, 2015) classifies various rules for application in building models according to their computational complexity and requirements imposed on the rule execution environment. It enables further advancement in the area of automated rule checking; (Fahad & Andrieux, 2016) presented how compliance checking of the rules can be performed by MVDXML and SWRL approaches; (Lee et al., 2019) proposes a design support system, using automatic rule checking to identify the compliance of rules and adopting Case-Based Reasoning (CBR) to provide recommendations. The module is based on CBR and consists of four parts, including ontology-semantics structure.

With regards to the research presented in this paper, (Uhm et al., 2015) asserts that hospitals required from 1000 to 3000 design rules whereas other types of buildings had fewer than 300 rules. This explains why hospitals are generally regarded as one of the most challenging building types to design (Delis & Delis, 1995) discusses the design and implementation of the Fire-Code Analyzer (FCA) prototype that is an expert system for fire-code checking. This FCA prototype has been used to examine architectural layouts from the domain of hospital buildings.

Decision support system overview

The architecture of proposed solution has several modules shown in Fig. 1, which provides a conceptual and functional review of health care building. The DSS is formed by main data sources, knowledge database, and CBR modules. Once the DSS is trained the information of building is provided by a standard file based on Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) and Green Building eXtended Markup Language (gbXML) specification (version 5.12). The result of the analysis is provided in a Report results.

2.1. Main data sources

The links to the main data sources are provided to the Heterogeneous Data Source Integration System (HDSIS). The proposed solution is based on the usage of information from public data sources. Thus, the proposed Decision Support System (DSS) is applied in Spain, according to the Technical Building Code, which it includes several regulations for electric, gas, thermal installations in buildings, accessibility, fire-prevention, pressure equipment, water, prevention of occupational hazards, etc. according to the facilities involved in the design of health care building. Some other regulations are Standardization Organizations, for example, some standard or regulations provided by UNE (Una Norma Española) or ISO (International Standard Organization). These sources are manually translated to rules which provide the main knowledge base.

Additionally, there are several databases available in different web pages from Statistical National Institute of Spain, and data from Ministerio de Sanidad of Spain: Health Information System, Sanitary data about medical discharge records of General Hospitals of National Sanitary System, and International Classification of Diseases (Diagnostics and Procedures). In addition, because of international aspects related to health care, there are some other data sources gathered from National Health Service from United Kingdom Government and Health Care System legislation and guidelines. These resources are the target of HDSIS, gathering the information automatically.

Some information from other health care facilities were exported to Green Building eXtended Markup Language (gbXML) and Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) files. This information is processed by a Case-based reasoning (CBR) to provide additional information about hospital design and the response of this facilities to the related population. The main designs included in the system corresponded to four different Andalusian hospitals, based on the populations of related locations. These hospitals were modified in some features to invalid status to provide fault cases and added additional facilities to provide additional valid cases.

Fig. 1. General Architecture of Decision Support System.

2.2. Heterogeneous data source Integration system (HDSIS).

The HDSIS is a system to gather information and integrate in unique structure of data. HDSIS is based on metadata mining, data mining, text mining, and decision support system (DSS) This structure can be gathered in two levels:

- **Metadata level.** The *meta*-information is integrated from different data sources, storing the link to the information. Thus, when the system needs a specific information, HDSIS check the information and collect it from the corresponding data sources.
- **Data level.** All *meta*-information and information are stored in a data warehouse, based on big data infrastructure.
- **Hybrid level.** According to the characteristics of the data source: size, granularity, volume, etc. some data sources are only integrated at metadata level and others at data level.

In this paper, HDSIS is briefly described in order to show the role in the proposed infrastructure. This paper is not focus on HDSIS, because this system was previously described in in (Guerrero et al., 2017).

2.3. Case-based reasoning

The CBR is a methodology for solving a variety of different nature problems. In this case, the CBR module (shown in Fig. 2) provides information about the different hospital or sanitary buildings. Conceptually, this information is about sanitary solutions for a specific population, taking this information joined to the information from population nearby to the sanitary building, CBR processes the information of positive and negative solutions for a specific population. The solution is considered as positive or negative, according to the percentage of time which one or more units in the hospital or sanitary building are swamped. This information is codified and provides a supervised learning approach to the final design got by the proposed solution.

The information retrieval module is used to extract information from standard file. This module provides a conceptual model of the health care building project, identifying the information gaps. Some gaps are provoked by errors in the interpretation of file or projects with lack information about facilities. In the performed test this module discarded the 2% of generated cases. These were not considered in the final analysis.

The information retrieval classifies the information in different levels

Fig. 2. Case-based reasoning module.

according to the detail and interpretation of different zones of the sanitary building, according to the Fig. 3. All specified installations in the sanitary building (included in the provided file) are identified and associated to a volume identification according to the DIN 277 – Areas and volumes of buildings and Building Technical Code. Additionally, the different volumes could be associated to a specific functionality according to the area and section. These areas and sections are estimated according to the availability of installation in the corresponding area and zone. The functional areas and sections are established according to

Fig. 3. Case-Based Reasoning Module.

DIN 13,080 – Division of hospitals into functional areas and functional sections. The estimation of functional areas and sections is made according to the data from the hospitals, except in case that the information is included in the provided files.

For each case, the system stores a scenario where an appropriate

Such that a higher value $\Omega_{Li}(q_i, c_i)$ denotes a higher acceptance of the value c_i of case c for the value q_i of a query q . Thus, the Composite Acceptance Function is composed by a composite function $\Omega: R \times \dots \times R \times R$ from the Local Acceptance Function Ω_{Li} (4) and it is based on Gauss Function.

$$\Omega((q_1, \dots, q_n), (c_1, \dots, c_n)) = \Omega_C(\Omega_{L1}(q_1, c_1), \dots, \Omega_{Ln}(q_n, c_n)) = \sum_{i=1}^n Gauss(q_i - c_i, a_i, v_i) \tag{4}$$

design is totally or partially adequate. Additionally, in certain situations, the final design may be an action with effects that are not a priori known and even not determined by the data given. This leads to an extension of the case concept to a triple: design, analysis, and outcomes. The analysis of a design provided faults and warnings. The fault is identified when the design does not accomplish any rule or constraints. The warning is identified when the design partially accomplishes any rule or constraint. The warnings or faults could take different effects or outcomes in the final design or project. The CBR is based on Global Acceptance Functions for Feature Vectors and Inductive Learning (Lenz, 1998). The Composite (Ω_C) and Global (Ω_G) Acceptance Functions are combined to implement two level case analysis. The Global Acceptance Function describes aggregated characteristics, The Composite Acceptance Function describes set of information entities or attributes defined in each domain.

$$\Omega_G : U \times U \rightarrow R \tag{1}$$

where $U := \text{domain}(\text{Attribute}_1) \times \dots \times \text{domain}(\text{Attribute}_n)$, such that a higher value $\Omega_G(q, c)$ denotes a higher acceptance of the case c for query q , so the Global Acceptance Function is defined as (2).

$$\alpha \equiv_q \beta \text{ if } \Omega_G(q, \alpha) \geq \Omega_G(q, \beta) \tag{2}$$

The acceptance functions provide the similarities between set of queries and cases. The computation of a global acceptance function regards correspondences of all set of information entities or attributes in the query and the cases, and extended correspondences enlarge the global acceptance. However, matching of information entities or attributes used for rejecting cases as well.

The Composite Acceptance Function is based on a Local (Ω_{Li}) Acceptance Function, which is defined separately for the attributes:

$$\Omega_{Li} : \text{domain}(\text{Attribute}_i) \times \text{domain}(\text{Attribute}_i) \rightarrow R \tag{3}$$

where a_i is the average of Attribute_i and v_i is the variance of c_i .

The Inductive Learning is applied to avoid the ambiguous terminology. Thus, the interpretation of certain pieces of information are context-sensitive and depends on several features, making the existing domain about the target design, in general too weak to allow for strong solving methods. Thus, the a_i and v_i parameters are validated using Inductive Learning for each Attribute_i or information entity of each case c_i . The Inductive Learning apply the entropy of attribute domain (D) and the conditional entropy of Attribute_i in case c_i to estimate the uncertainty range of a_i and v_i for case c_i .

$$E_D(\text{Attribute}_i) = \sum_{j=1}^k -f_j \log_2 f_j \tag{5}$$

$$E_D(c_i / \text{Attribute}_i) = \sum_{j=1}^k -f_j \sum_{u=1}^s fr_{j,u} \log_2 fr_{j,u} \tag{6}$$

In equation (5), let f_j is the frequency of value j of Attribute_i and k is the number of different values of Attribute_i . In equation (6) let $fr_{j,u}$ the relative frequency of value j of the Attribute_i respect other values of attributes (let s the number of these possible combinations) on the case c_i . The final entropy is the difference between (5) and (6) and it is applied as a modification factor in the determination of a_i and v_i .

2.4. Reinforcement learning

Additionally, the report is manually validated, providing a general score. This score is applied as part of a RL algorithm. The RL methodology fits a problem setting known as a Markov decision process (MDP) with model-based policy optimization (Janner et al., 2019), in which the

outcome of applying any action to any design depends only on that action and that design as opposed to being dependent on preceding actions or designs. The RL algorithm is applied when a design or project is analyzed again or with other projects with similarities (same zones, same population features, etc.), comparing the previous report results with the new report results, reinforcing the reduction of faults and warnings. Additionally, the RL algorithm uses the detailed information about population of the related zone evaluating the adequacy of health care building for the corresponding population.

The goal of RL is to find the optimal policy π^* (7) that maximizes the expected sum of discounted rewards.

$$\pi^* = \underset{\pi}{\operatorname{argmax}} E_{\pi} \left[\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \gamma^t R(c_t, c_{t+1}) \right] \quad (7)$$

where γ^t is the discount factor, with values between 0 and 1. The R is the reward function based on the differences between cases c_t and c_{t+1} , according to the scope of regulations complaining by the case.

Each module stores the information in the Knowledge Database. The Knowledge Database is used by Report Generator to provide the Report results. This module implements a parser and converter to the Report results, which is in XML format.

3. Experimental results

The proposed solution was tested in two scenarios. The first set was a high complexity set with hospital designs, which involves different types of zones and installations; and the second set was with primary health care designs based on student designs.

3.1. Hospital building evaluation

The proposed system was tested with a health care building project. This project was randomly modified in different aspects, based on the IFC and gbXML files. The different models created are detailed in Table 1. All these projects were analyzed in two scenarios: independently and taking advantage from RL algorithm. The analysis of both scenarios is made based on confusion matrix (Diez, 2018) and confusion metrics (accuracy, misclassification, precision, sensitivity aka recall, and specificity).

In the independently application case, the starting status after training stage of proposed system is stored. The starting status is restored after each analysis and the results are not applied by means RL algorithm. Thus, the RL based on the recursive application in the same case is disabled. The results of application in the cases proposed in Table 1 are shown in Table 2. According to the data provided in Table 2, some confusion metrics: Accuracy = 75%, Misclassification = 25 %, Precision = 50%, Sensitivity aka Recall = 100%, Specificity = 66,67%. The confusion metrics are a main representation of features of proposed method, showing the successful of this approach.

However, the application of RL algorithm could increase the efficiency of process, improving the accuracy of algorithm in different solutions of the same scenario. The main problem is the identification and

Table 1
Description of Hospital building cases.

Number of solutions	Type of solution	Description
16	Correct solutions	Including the original project, other 15 solutions to the proposed design could be valid.
36	Incorrect solutions	These projects have different aspects which are not valid according to the current regulations.
12	Incomplete solutions	These projects provided health care buildings which incomplete services or lack with support according to the related population.
64	Total number of solutions	

Table 2
Confusion Matrix for Analysis without RL.

Variants classified by the algorithm		Reference variant set	
		Positive	Negative
Positive		16	16
Negative		0	32

Table 3
Confusion Matrix for Analysis with RL.

Variants classified by the algorithm		Reference variant set	
		Positive	Negative
Positive		16	6
Negative		0	42

delimitation of spaces. Thus, there are some incomplete solutions (Table 1) that provoked space recognition mistakes. So, additionally, the RL algorithm associates a weight to each space interpretation (from file), this weight is increased according to the different iterations, increasing the weight of the best space solution. The result of this new feature is the reduction Positive-Negative case, increasing the efficiency and accuracy of system. The results are shown in Table 3, getting the following confusion metrics: Accuracy = 90,63%, Misclassification = 9,38%, Precision = 72,73%, Sensitivity aka Recall = 100%, Specificity = 87,5 %. The comparison of independently and RL algorithm is shown in Table 4. In both cases, the sensitivity is 100%, but the accuracy, precision, and specificity are increased, additionally the misclassification is decreased. Thus, the best solution is reached with the RL algorithm.

3.2. Primary health care building Evaluation.

Additionally, the University of Seville includes a graduate degree in health engineering. One of the curriculum assignments is Hospital Facilities. In this subject, students must design a Primary Care Centre for a generic population of 2000 inhabitants. Since 2017, students have developed different buildings including the necessary outbuildings and related facilities. The proposed system is used to improve the students' design, detecting possible errors on it and providing the report of accomplished and unaccomplished regulations. Thus, since 2017 a total number of 183 Primary Health Care Centres has been mainly evaluated by the system using the RL algorithm, because the students test several times the different Primary Health Care Centres, but the approach without RL was evaluated, too. The 183 cases were improved in 5 different practices, in which the student adds new installations and check the validity on the proposed solution. These make a total of 915 different cases. The main differences between Primary Health Care Centres and Hospital are the size, the complexity of installation, and the variety of clinical services. These Centres are usually composed by several consulting room, infirmary, emergency room, waiting room, toilets, administration office, patient service, machine room, stores, conference room, personnel sitting room, offices, and, in some cases, students could improve the Centre with additional health services: paediatrics zone, etc. In these cases, the results are better because of the complexity of installations and the distribution of zones. Table 5 shows the confusion matrix without RL, Table 6 shows the confusion matrix

Table 4
Comparing without and with RL.

Confusion Metrics	Without RL	With RL
Accuracy	75 %	90,63 %
Misclassification	25 %	9,38 %
Precision	50 %	72,73 %
Sensitivity aka Recall	100 %	100 %
Specificity	66,67 %	87,50 %

Table 5
Confusion Matrix for Analysis without RL.

Variants classified by the algorithm		Reference variant set	
		Positive	Negative
Variants classified by the algorithm	Positive	207	82
	Negative	0	626

Table 6
Confusion Matrix for Analysis with RL.

Variants classified by the algorithm		Reference variant set	
		Positive	Negative
Variants classified by the algorithm	Positive	207	53
	Negative	0	655

Table 7
Comparing without and with RL.

Confusion Metrics	Without RL	With RL
Accuracy	91,04 %	94,21 %
Misclassification	8,96 %	5,79 %
Precision	71,63 %	79,62 %
Sensitivity aka Recall	100 %	100 %
Specificity	88,42 %	92,51%

with RL, and Table 7 shows the comparison between both cases. Thus, the accuracy, specificity, and precision are increased when the complexity of building is reduced. In the same way, the misclassification is reduced.

4. Conclusions

The proposed solution provided a quick form to check and validate the design or project about health care facility building, according to the current regulation. This framework makes novel contributions to the current scenario of Spanish health care buildings:

- The health care facility buildings need to consider a great quantity of constraints and parameters, which involves specialized and high qualified knowledge.
- The check and validation of regulations in a health care building is a task with high financial, time, and personnel cost. The proposed solution reduces these costs providing a report of results.
- The recursive application of proposed solution on different evolutions of the same project or design, is involved in a RL process to increase the efficiency of the solution.
- The system only uses the information in a standard file format (IFC and gbXML), this information could be provided by Building Information Model (BIM) applications, and it will not require any additional requirements.
- The proposed system is used as an educational support tool, in order to improve the skills of the students in the design of Hospital Facilities.
- The application of this framework updating the regulations in the knowledge base.
- The proposed solution could be used to provide an educational purpose, providing a validation method for the project designed by students, or using the report results as a tool to show the weaknesses of different projects.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

J.I. Guerrero: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Resources, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision,

Project administration, Funding acquisition. **G. Miró-Amarante:** Methodology, Validation, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **A. Martín:** Conceptualization, Software, Validation, Investigation, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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